

UNSTEADY FLOW CONTROL MECHANISMS OF CASING TREATMENT ACROSS
REYNOLDS NUMBERS IN TRANSONIC AXIAL FAN ROTORS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates Reynolds-number (Re)-dependent unsteady stabilization mechanisms of axial slot casing treatment (ASCT) in a transonic axial fan rotor. Experimentally validated time-resolved simulations were conducted at two representative Re , emulating ground and high-altitude conditions. Stall mechanism differences between the two Re were clarified via tip power spectrum characteristics and temporal flow field evolution. With ASCT, stall margins increased by 42.1% (ground, Ref. Re) and 48.6% (high altitude, Low Re). Phase-resolved diagnostics of mass flow rate, momentum flux through the slot, and their coupling with tip dynamics revealed distinct extraction/reinjection behaviors: At Ref. Re , tip flow is dominated by tip leakage vortex (TLV)-shock interactions; the slot generates phase-symmetric, high-amplitude extraction/reinjection pulses, acting as a transient momentum exchanger

to disrupt TLV-shock feedback. At low Re , pronounced radial migration and suction-side separation occur; the slot exhibits sustained suction bias (extraction impulse exceeding reinjection by $\sim 11.3\%$), suppressing radial migration and reducing intermittent separation. Proper Orthogonal Decomposition analysis validated dominant stall structures and post-ASCT flow distributions. Notably, tip flow fluctuations became similar with ASCT applied for both Re . Phase-triggered averages based on net slot momentum flux revealed divergent stabilization mechanisms: at Low Re , the leading POD mode is phase-shifted relative to net slot momentum flux, unlike that at Ref. Re . These results clarify the modal underpinnings of ASCT's dual-regime stabilization and offer engineering metrics to guide Re -adaptive passive casing treatment design.

Keywords: Fan, Aerodynamics, Stability Enhancement

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NOMENCLATURE

c_{ax}	Axial chord
y^+	Dimensionless distance from wall
π	Total pressure ratio
ω	Vorticity
ω_r	Normalized radial vorticity
H_n	Normalized helicity
U_{tip}	Tangential velocity at blade tip
T_{BPP}	Blade passing period
f_{BPF}	Blade passing frequency
TLF	Tip leakage flow
TLV	Tip leakage vortex
SV	Separation vortex
RSV	Radial separation vortex
CT	Casing treatment
M_r	Radial momentum flux
I_r	Radial momentum impulse
POD	Proper Orthogonal Decomposition
a_k	Time coefficients
Φ	Orthonormal spatial modes
KE	Modal kinetic energy

1. INTRODUCTION

The challenge of concurrently optimizing aerodynamic efficiency and stall margin is particularly acute for transonic fan rotors in high-altitude unmanned aerial vehicles. At such flight conditions, the Reynolds number (Re) decreases dramatically, intensifying viscous effects and altering fundamental flow physics. As a result, transonic rotors at low Re experience compounded performance degradation—where intensified radial migration couples with tip leakage flows (TLFs) to precipitate severe stall margin losses. The difficulty of achieving stable operation under these conditions underscores the importance of understanding the Re -dependent stall inception mechanisms [1].

Previous investigations have highlighted the strong influence of Re on fan/compressor aerodynamics. Choi et al. [2] showed that reducing Re modifies endwall separation and shock structures, thereby changing stall onset. Li et al. [3] demonstrated, via dynamic mode decomposition, that Re alters TLF spectra and the associated stall modes. Hutchings and Hall [4–6] observed experimentally that below a critical Re , pre-stall and in-stall flow structures become increasingly three-dimensional and unsteady. Ren et al. [7] synthesized these findings, emphasizing that Re -specific stabilization strategies are essential for transonic compressors. Collectively, these works confirm that reduced Re transforms stall inception physics, yet the blade tip remains the critical region.

Casing treatments (CTs) have long been recognized as an effective passive means to improve stall margin by modifying tip flows. Decades of research, most recently reviewed by Yoon and

Cargill [8], have reaffirmed the potential of CTs for practical applications. Among various designs, axial slots consistently yield the most significant improvements. While extensive research has explored their stabilization mechanisms [9–22], their effect is widely linked to extraction and reinjection. Recent studies have offered insights from different perspectives, reflecting the complexity of the issue: Chen et al. [23] employed a complex axial slot with opposite skew angles on its extraction and reinjection sides, and found that the extraction skew angle is critical for stall margin enhancement, while the reinjection skew angle is more relevant to aerodynamic efficiency. Martin and Rodriguez [24] demonstrated that a rear cavity alters front-edge momentum exchange, trading loss reduction for smaller stall-margin gains. Dai et al. [25] applied proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) to distinguish between oscillation-attenuation and tip leakage vortex (TLV)-energizing mechanisms depending on the relative circumferential positions of extraction and reinjection. Zhao et al. [26] further confirmed that axial slots remain effective across Re regimes, and noted that extraction and reinjection characteristics exhibit significant differences across different Re regimes. However, the stabilization physics of CTs under high-altitude Re conditions are still poorly understood—particularly the relative contributions of extraction and reinjection, and how these two processes differ from those at ground- Re remain unclarified.

Two unresolved questions therefore motivate the present study. First, what precise stall inception pathways dominate at different Re , particularly how the balance shifts between TLV–shock interactions at ground conditions and radial-migration–induced suction-side separation at high-altitude conditions. Second, by what unsteady mechanisms—at the level of extraction and reinjection—do axial-slot casing treatments adapt to stabilize these distinct flow regimes. To address these questions, this paper employs time-resolved URANS simulations of a transonic axial fan rotor across both ground- and high-altitude Re , coupled with POD to identify dominant coherent structures. This framework allows a direct comparison between baseline stall inception dynamics and the slot-modified flow fields, revealing how the temporal and spatial signatures of extraction and reinjection vary with Re .

2. METHODOLOGIES

This study utilizes a wide-chord transonic axial fan rotor designed by the Institute of Engineering Thermophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences. The rotor consists of 18 blades. The hub-to-tip ratios at the rotor inlet and outlet are 0.31 and 0.56, respectively, and the tip clearance is 0.94% c_{ax} at the tip. The inlet tip Mach number is 1.38. The aspect ratio is 1.42, and the solidity at the tip is 1.47.

The Re for fan operation is defined using inlet parameters as $Re=ul/v$, where l denotes the blade tip chord length, u represents the inlet average velocity, and v stands for the kinematic viscosity derived from inlet conditions. Our previous work [26] has established that the critical Re (Re_{crit}) of the fan under investigation is approximately 200,000. To explore the stall margin improvement mechanism of axial slots under

varying Re , two representative conditions were selected around Re_{crit} : *Ref. Re* ($Re \approx 2Re_{crit}$) and *Low Re* ($Re \approx 0.2Re_{crit}$).

2.1 Casing treatment configuration

It was confirmed that for the two Re values investigated in this work, the optimal axial position of the slots on the blade tip lies around 50% c_{ax} . At this position, the configuration not only suppresses the blockage region induced by the shock wave-TLV interaction under high Re but also mitigates the radial migration and leading-edge overflow under low Re . Building upon this finding, the treated casing with this specific configuration is adopted in the present study. A schematic of the CT is illustrated in Fig. 1, and its nondimensional design parameters are summarized in Table 1.

FIGURE 1: SCHEMATIC OF THE CASING TREATMENT DESIGN

TABLE 1: CASING TREATMENT DESIGN PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Slot length L_{CT}/c_{ax}	1.00
Slot depth d_{CT}/c_{ax}	0.35
Slot width $s_{CT,open}/c_{\theta}$	0.25
Slot axial location L_a/c_{ax}	0.50
Open area ratio $s_{CT,open}/s_{CT}$	0.50
Slot angle to radial	45°

2.2 Computational Approach

ANSYS CFX was employed for steady and unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes simulations. Steady-state simulations were first performed to obtain the baseline fan’s total-pressure-ratio and isentropic-efficiency characteristic curves. The resulting converged flow field then served as the initial condition for subsequent unsteady calculations of both the baseline fan and the tip-injection configuration. Temporal discretization was carried out with a second-order backward-Euler scheme. Spatial discretization of all convective

terms—both in the Navier–Stokes and turbulence-transport equations—employed a second-order, bounded, high-resolution advection scheme. CFX’s automatic fluid-time-scale control was enabled to adjust the physical time step dynamically, ensuring stable convergence and solution accuracy. The Shear-Stress-Transport (SST $k-\omega$) turbulence model [27, 28] was used to model the Reynolds stresses, and the well-validated $\gamma-Re_{\theta t}$ transition model [29, 30], commonly employed in low- Re compressor studies [31, 32], was used to capture laminar-to-turbulent transition.

Meshes were generated in NUMECA Autogrid5 (rotor) and IGG (CT). The rotor passage mesh featured an O-4H topology, while the CT used a butterfly topology (Fig. 2). Each rotor passage contained approximately 1.3 million nodes, with a surrounding O-block of 227 nodes enclosing the blade. In the tip-clearance region, 17 cells were clustered in the radial direction to resolve TLFs and associated vortical structures. This mesh has achieved grid independence, as validated by previous studies on this fan rotor [33, 34]. Each CT slot contains approximately 40,000 grid points. A transient rotor–stator interface treated the rotor/CT coupling. Fine grid refinement was applied near all solid boundaries, with the first grid layer height set to 2×10^{-6} m. The mesh was adjusted such that the dimensionless wall distance (y^+) converged to an average value of approximately 1.

Adiabatic, no-slip boundary conditions were imposed on all solid walls. At the rotor inlet, total pressure and total temperature were specified according to the International Standard Atmosphere. Outlet static pressure followed a simple radial-equilibrium relation, varied to obtain different operating points. Each rotor passage covering 20° in the circumferential direction was simulated over 60 physical time steps, with ten inner iterations performed within each time step.

FIGURE 2: MESH DETAILS OF THE ROTOR AND CT SLOT

2.3 Validation

Experiments were performed on a single-stage fan, with the numerical methodology validated against full-stage

measurement data. The rotor and stator assembly uses ~ 2 million mesh nodes. Tests covered two Re conditions, yielding performance characteristics. Detailed experimental procedures are reported in our prior work [26]; only validation results are presented here.

In Fig. 3, mass flow rate (abscissa) is normalized by the near-choke mass flow rate from the computational model. At *Ref. Re*, numerical results agree well with experiments. At *Low Re*, predictions slightly overestimate the total pressure ratio but accurately capture experimental trends. This close agreement across both conditions confirms the numerical methodology's validity and supports the reliability of subsequent conclusions on the fan's aerodynamic behavior and performance.

FIGURE 3: COMPARISON OF SIMULATED AND TEST DATA: (a) FAN CHARACTERISTIC AND (b) SPANWISE DISTRIBUTION

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Unsteady Flow Characteristics at Different Re

Given the significant differences in stall mechanisms under varying Re , it is essential to first establish the stall inception mechanism of the baseline fan before examining how the CT modifies stall margin. The axial velocity V_z is adopted as the primary fluctuation indicator, as it directly reflects both the flow-handling capability of the fan and the onset of stall. Figure 4 shows the temporal evolution of axial velocity at monitoring points near the blade tip leading edge under near-stall condition (monitoring points arranged along the chordwise direction in the relative coordinate system). The axial velocity and time is nondimensionalized by the blade tip tangential velocity U_{tip} and the blade passing period (T_{BPP}), respectively. The fluctuation periods are measured to be $0.8083T_{BPP}$ (T_{Ref}) at *Ref. Re* and $2.55T_{BPP}$ (T_{Low}) at *Low Re*, with the fluctuation amplitude also smaller at *Low Re*.

Figure 5 presents the power spectrum $PS_{V_z/U_{tip}}$ distribution of the nondimensional axial velocity near the blade tip. The abscissa denotes frequency normalized by the blade passing frequency (f_{BPP}), while the ordinate represents the nondimensional axial distance from the leading to trailing edge. At *Ref. Re*, a distinct frequency component at $1.237f_{BPP}$ (f_{Ref}) and its second harmonic can be observed. The higher-amplitude regions of f_{Ref} are concentrated from the leading edge to approximately $20\% c_{ax}$, while the $2f_{Ref}$ component appears with

lower amplitude around $10\% c_{ax}$. At *Low Re*, the dominant frequency shifts to $0.392f_{BPP}$ (f_{Low}) and $0.784f_{BPP}$ ($2f_{Low}$). Notably, the amplitude of $2f_{Low}$ exceeds that of f_{Low} , with the high-energy region concentrated between $40\% c_{ax}$ and the trailing edge. This observation suggests that $2f_{Low}$ is not merely a nonlinear harmonic of f_{Low} , but originates from an additional unsteady flow mechanism, which will be analyzed in detail in the following part. These spectral differences reveal fundamentally distinct stall mechanisms at different Re , and identifying the associated flow features forms the core objective of this section.

FIGURE 4: COMPARISON OF NORMALIZED AXIAL VELOCITY FLUCTUATIONS AT LEADING EDGE: (a) REF. RE AND (b) LOW RE

FIGURE 5: COMPARISON OF POWER SPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF THE NORMALIZED AXIAL VELOCITY AT BLADE TIP: (a) REF. RE AND (b) LOW RE

At *Ref. Re*, the spectrum at the tip probe exhibits a strong f_{Ref} component and its second harmonic. However, no coherent structure corresponding to $2f_{Ref}$ is identifiable in the flow field, suggesting that the second harmonic arises from nonlinear distortion of the fundamental oscillation rather than an independent instability. Thus, the dominant unsteadiness is governed by f_{Ref} . To clarify its physical origin, Fig. 6 presents instantaneous snapshots of the blade tip flow field at five instants spanning $1.25T_{Ref}$. The first and second rows depict nondimensional axial velocity and radial vorticity distributions, while the third row illustrates vortex structures (identified using the Ω criterion and colored by nondimensional helicity) along with TLF streamlines. Analysis of the axial velocity distribution reveals multiple low-velocity regions near the blade tip. Two regions are of particular significance: Region A, downstream of the shock, and Region B, at the pressure-side leading edge, marked with dashed blue and black lines, respectively. As Region B convects to $\sim 20\% c_{ax}$, Region A reappears at the pressure-side leading edge, initiating a new cycle. This indicates that Region A represents an earlier stage of Region B, consistent with the strong spectral amplitude observed near the leading

edge. The physical mechanism can be further clarified through the vortex fields: the TLV rapidly expands and breaks down after passing through the shock, with the resulting vortex clusters impinging upon the pressure surface and modulating tip loading. This feedback alters the TLV strength, forming a self-sustained oscillatory loop. Such a feedback cycle—distinct from externally forced responses—accounts for the persistent f_{Ref} component.

This phenomenon is similar to the self-excited unsteadiness observed by Du et al. [35] but occurs at a higher frequency. Besides, the cycle also induces suction-side separation with the same periodicity, although its spectral amplitude is weaker and less dominant in shaping the tip flow, a point corroborated in subsequent modal analyses.

FIGURE 6: TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF INSTANTANEOUS NONDIMENSIONAL AXIAL VELOCITY, RADIAL VORTICITY, AND TLF STREAMLINES AT 98% SPAN FOR REF. RE CONDITION (VORTEX STRUCTURES COLORED BY NORMALIZED HELICITY)

At low Re , a much thicker boundary layer promotes stronger radial migration along the suction surface, fundamentally altering the stall dynamics. Figure 7 illustrates eight snapshots over one T_{Low} , displaying nondimensional axial velocity, radial vorticity, and vortex structures with secondary flow streamlines at the blade tip. A pronounced low-velocity region (Region A), highlighted by a red dashed line, is observed near the trailing edge. Within one T_{Low} cycle, Region A convects from the suction surface to the adjacent pressure surface and detaches at the trailing edge, corresponding to the strong f_{Low} spectral component localized near the trailing edge. Simultaneously, a separation zone (Region B) forms near the suction-side leading edge shock position, delineated with a black dashed line. The intensity of Region B increases progressively, producing a downstream low-velocity region that expands continuously. At $t=4/8T_{Low}$, Region B initiates a new separation cycle, such that within one cycle of Region A, Region B undergoes two oscillation cycles—corresponding to the $2f_{Low}$ component in the spectrum.

The origins of these dual frequencies can be explained by the vortex and secondary flow fields. At low Re , weakened

shocks and thicker boundary layers result in more coherent but less unstable TLVs, while radial migration generates a variety of interacting vortical structures. Three distinct vortex types are identified: the TLV, the separation vortex (SV), and the radial separation vortex (RSV). Here, emphasis is placed on the migration-induced mechanisms. The SV oscillates in strength in concert with Region B, while the RSV forms and decays periodically, matching the convective behavior of Region A. Notably, the SV aligns approximately with the streamwise direction, whereas the RSV is oriented radially. Furthermore, the RSV’s oscillation period (T_{Low}) is twice that of the SV ($0.5T_{Low}$), requiring further explanation. The directional discrepancy between these two vortex structures can be elucidated from the perspective of the vorticity transport equation, expressed as Eq. (1):

$$\frac{D\omega}{Dt} = (\omega \cdot \nabla)u - \omega(\nabla \cdot u) + \nu \nabla^2 \omega + \frac{\nabla \rho \times \nabla p}{\rho^2} + \nabla \times \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \cdot \tau \right). \quad (1)$$

The terms on the right-hand side represent vorticity stretching and tilting, dilatation, baroclinic vorticity generation, viscous diffusion, and the curl of viscous stress, respectively. Formation

of both SV and RSV is linked to radial migration. On the suction surface, radial inflow impinges on the boundary layer and induces separation. Under a strong adverse pressure gradient, the baroclinic term becomes dominant, generating new vorticity aligned primarily with the main flow. Simultaneously, the boundary-layer shear enhances streamwise vorticity, but the radial migration here is insufficient to reorient it significantly, hence the SV remains streamwise-aligned. Conversely, during upstream propagation and subsequent deflection by mainstream convection, radial migration redistributes the vorticity within the thickened suction-side boundary layer, tilting and amplifying it into radial components. The resulting RSV core is therefore oriented radially. However, lacking continuous energy input, the

RSV dissipates rapidly downstream through mixing with the mainstream, following an “expansion–dissipation” cycle. The streamwise-oriented SV oscillates with period $0.5T_{Low}$, reflecting direct forcing by the periodic boundary-layer separation under adverse pressure gradients. This represents a linear response to the intrinsic unsteadiness of radial migration impinging upon the suction surface. In contrast, the RSV oscillates at T_{Low} , emerging from the nonlinear tilting and stretching of accumulated axial vorticity by successive migration pulses. Its development requires constructive phasing over multiple cycles, explaining its doubled period. The coexistence of $0.5T_{Low}$ - and T_{Low} -period structures therefore reflects distinct source terms in the vorticity transport balance at different axial locations.

FIGURE 7: TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF INSTANTANEOUS NONDIMENSIONAL AXIAL VELOCITY, RADIAL VORTICITY, AND SECONDARY FLOW STREAMLINES AT 98% SPAN FOR LOW RE CONDITION(VORTEX STRUCTURES COLORED BY NORMALIZED HELICITY)

3.2 Effects of Casing Treatment on Unsteady Flow Dynamics

The complexity of tip flow fields and stall mechanisms at different Re has motivated the adoption of ASCT. The following section investigates the underlying mechanisms of ASCT. Since the primary objective of this study is to clarify the stall margin improvement mechanism, the influence of ASCT on fan efficiency is not considered. Figure 8 compares the total pressure ratio characteristics without and with the application of ASCT at different Re . The stall margin improvement is 42.1% at $Ref. Re$ and 48.6% at $Low Re$, confirming that ASCT provides a pronounced stall margin extension across Re . The definition of stall margin improvement is given as follows:

$$\Delta SM = \left[\left(\frac{m_{SC} \pi_{NS}}{m_{CT} \pi_{SC}} \right)_{NS} - 1 \right] \times 100\% . \quad (2)$$

Figure 9 presents the power spectrum $PS_{Vz/Utip}$ distribution with the CT applied. It can be observed that the $4f_{BPF}$ component emerges prominently in both Re conditions. This phenomenon can be attributed to the interaction between the four slots within each blade passage and the 18 rotor blades: the periodic disturbances induced by these four slots superimpose with the f_{BPF} , and the unsteady energy undergoes constructive interference at the $4f_{BPF}$ harmonic, thus leading to its dominance. The focus of subsequent investigations will be placed on the near-stall conditions of the baseline configuration with and without CT, aiming to elucidate the aerodynamic mechanisms

underlying stall margin improvement and performance regulation.

FIGURE 8: COMPARISON OF TOTAL PRESSURE RATIO CHARACTERISTICS WITHOUT AND WITH CT APPLIED

FIGURE 9: COMPARISON OF POWER SPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF THE NORMALIZED AXIAL VELOCITY AT BLADE TIP WITH THE CT APPLIED: (a) REF. RE AND (b) LOW RE

Figure 10 compares the mass exchange between the main flow passage and the slots under various Re . The control surface is defined at the slot openings on the main flow path, where the surfaces are colored by normalized radial velocity. A positive radial velocity (red) denotes inflow into the slots, whereas a negative velocity (blue) denotes outflow from the slots. The slots are labeled from S1 to S4, with S3 located above the rotor tip leading edge at the selected instant. Each slot exhibits a periodic pattern synchronized with the T_{BPP} . The slot phasing is given by

$$\varphi_{slots} = \frac{360^\circ}{(N_{slots/blade} \times N_{blades})} \quad (3)$$

Since $N_{slots/blade}=4$, visualizing four slots simultaneously is equivalent to observing four equally spaced instants of one slot. For reference, the normalized axial velocity at the rotor tip (98% span) is also provided. After applying ASCT, the tip flow fields exhibit similar qualitative features under both conditions. However, the radial velocities of fluid entering and leaving the slots at $Low Re$ are markedly smaller than those at $Ref. Re$, mainly due to the lower pressure ratio and weaker shock strength. Despite these similarities, differences in extraction and reinjection behavior persist between the two cases, motivating the detailed analysis presented below.

FIGURE 10: DISTRIBUTION OF NONDIMENSIONAL RADIAL VELOCITY ON SLOT OPENINGS

Figure 11(a) compares the ratio of extraction to reinjection mass flow rate within one T_{BPP} at $Ref. Re$ and $Low Re$ conditions. To highlight differences, the ratio is plotted in logarithmic scale, with vertical markers indicating the blade passing instants at slots S1–S4. The curve at $Ref. Re$ is relatively steep, reflecting stall margin improvement achieved through periodic strong extraction and reinjection. In contrast, the curve at $Low Re$ is smoother, suggesting that stabilization relies more on sustained and moderate extraction and reinjection. Figure 11(b) illustrates the temporal evolution of net mass flow rate through the slot openings at different Re , with flow entering the slot defined as positive and flow leaving the slot as negative. The net slot mass flow rate is given by the superposition of these two components. To enable direct comparison, the mass flow rate is normalized by their respective peak values at each Re . Distinct differences are observed, particularly as the blade passes S2 and S4. A sharp peak arises near S2, likely due to the sudden increase in extraction mass flow rate driven by local flow migration. The discrepancies near S4 are more complex and warrant further discussion.

FIGURE 11: TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF SLOT OPENING MASS FLOW RATES: (a) RATIO OF EXTRACTION TO REINJECTION MASS FLOW RATE AND (b) NORMALIZED NET MASS FLOW RATE

To explain these differences, Figure 12 contrasts the extraction and reinjection flow rates within one T_{BPP} , also normalized by peak extraction. While the phasing of extraction and reinjection remains similar across Re , their temporal variations differ markedly. In particular, Slot S2 lies near the suction surface where radial migration is strongest, accounting for the sharp extraction increase observed. At Slot S3, located above the blade tip leading edge, a extraction peak forms across both Re . Here, the slot extraction region lies downstream of the

shock, where a strong pressure gradient induces this peak. At Slot S4, reinjection mass flow rate is relatively small at *Ref. Re* but becomes comparable to extraction mass flow rate at *Low Re*, causing a delayed reinjection peak. Moreover, at *Ref. Re* the extraction and reinjection durations are nearly balanced, with a steep injection profile, whereas at *Low Re* reinjection is steadier and more gradual.

FIGURE 12: TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF SLOT EXTRACTION AND REINJECTION MASS FLOW RATES: (A) REF. RE (B) LOW RE

The distinct timing features of extraction and reinjection under different *Re* highlight the need to evaluate their relative dominance within one cycle. The extraction/reinjection momentum flux, M_r , is defined as the instantaneous radial action intensity exerted by the slots on the passage flow. Integration of M_r over one T_{BPP} yields the net radial impulse per cycle, which is nondimensionalized by the mainstream impulse above 80% span at the inlet to define the impulse coefficient, I_r . The extraction and reinjection impulses, together with their variations under different *Re*, are summarized in Table 2. Results indicate that the instantaneous effect of the slots is considerably stronger at *Ref. Re* than that at *Low Re*, consistent with the higher aerodynamic loading. At *Ref. Re*, extraction and reinjection impulses are nearly equal, indicating that both processes play comparable roles: extraction removes low-energy fluid while reinjection re-energizes the mainstream. By contrast, at *Low Re*, the extraction impulse exceeds the reinjection impulse by approximately 11.3%. This demonstrates that extraction is dominant at *Low Re*, and sustained extraction is critical for suppressing radial migration effects on the tip flow. This observation is consistent with the peak near S2 in Figure 11(b).

In summary, CT functions as an instantaneous momentum exchanger at *Ref. Re*, where stall margin improvement is achieved through strong periodic extraction and reinjection. At *Low Re*, however, ASCT acts as a sustained extraction stabilizer, mitigating radial migration and providing robust stall suppression.

$$M_r = \iint_{S_{slot}} \rho V_r^2 dS \quad (4)$$

$$I_r = \frac{\int_0^{T_{BPP}} M_r(t) dt}{\rho V_z^2 A_{tip} T_{BPP}} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta M_r = M_{r,Extraction} - M_{r,Reinjection} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta I_r = I_{r,Extraction} - I_{r,Reinjection} \quad (7)$$

TABLE 2: NET RADIAL IMPULSE PER CYCLE

	$I_r, Extraction$	$I_r, Reinjection$	ΔI_r
<i>Ref. Re</i>	0.6715	0.6759	-0.0044
<i>Low Re</i>	0.5625	0.4987	0.0638

FIGURE 13: TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF NET RADIAL MOMENTUM FLUX AT SLOT OPENING: (A) REF. RE (B) LOW RE

3.3 POD-Based Analysis of Flow Control Mechanisms

To further elucidate the *Re* dependence of CT stabilization, particularly the role of extraction and reinjection through axial slots, a Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) analysis was conducted on the unsteady flow fields. In this study, POD was applied to the axial velocity field at 98% span, such that the modal energy is directly linked to the kinetic energy (KE) of velocity fluctuations. For clarity on the POD results, relevant background is provided herein. This study adopted the covariance matrix approach to implement POD, a classic technique for decomposing time-resolved flow fields. The method processes a set of "snapshots"—time-step axial velocity data from CFD simulations, with the mean removed and reshaped into vectors—to extract dominant flow structures and their temporal variations. The key procedure involves first constructing a covariance matrix $C = U^T U / N$, where U denotes the snapshot matrix (each column corresponds to a preprocessed axial velocity snapshot) and N is the total number of snapshots. Solving the eigenvalue problem $C v_k = \sigma_k v_k$ generates eigenvalues σ_k and their associated eigenvectors v_k . Spatial modes of the axial velocity field are obtained as $\Phi_k = U v_k / \sqrt{N \sigma_k}$, which characterize the dominant flow structures. Temporal evolution of these modes is reflected in modal coefficients $a_{k,i} = \Phi_k^T \tilde{V}_{z,i}$ with $\tilde{V}_{z,i}$ being the i -th snapshot vector. Notably, the eigenvalues σ_k directly quantify the energy contribution of each mode: the total KE of axial velocity fluctuations across all snapshots equals the sum of all eigenvalues, while the k -th mode's KE of fluctuations is proportional to its eigenvalue. This relationship makes the eigenvalue a direct measure of each mode's energetic significance. For additional details on the covariance matrix-based POD, refer to [36]. Figure 14 compares the energy distribution of the first ten POD modes at two *Re*, both without and with CT. For the baseline configuration at *Ref. Re*, more than

95% KE is concentrated in the first two modes, reflecting a relatively simple stall mechanism. At *Low Re*, however, the energy is distributed across the first four modes, indicating more complex unsteady dynamics. With CT applied, both *Re* conditions collapse back to a two-mode-dominated system, although the *Low-Re* case shows a more balanced energy distribution between the two leading modes compared with *Ref. Re*, suggesting subtle differences in the flow response.

FIGURE 14: COMPARISON OF KINETIC ENERGY PROPORTION DISTRIBUTIONS OF THE FIRST 10 POD MODES

Since each pair of modes forms a conjugate pair, analysis can focus on the first two pairs, which account for more than 90% KE in all cases. Representative spatial structures of these dominant modes are shown in Figs. 15 and 16 for the smooth casing and treated casing cases, all evaluated near the stability limit of smooth cases. The top row illustrates mean-subtracted axial velocity snapshots—the input fields to POD—while the subsequent rows display the extracted modal structures. Dark and light contours should be interpreted as fluctuation intensities rather than velocity deficits or surpluses. For the baseline rotor at *Ref. Re*, the first mode pair captures TLV breakdown and its periodic propagation from the leading edge to the pressure side, accounting for 95.6% KE and thus dominating the stall inception process. In contrast, at *Low Re*, the stall mechanism involves two coupled unsteady modes: the first mode pair (56.8%) is associated with periodic intensification of suction-side SV, while the second mode pair (35.3%) corresponds to the RSV from the suction surface toward the adjacent pressure side, accompanied by trailing-edge vortex shedding. The coexistence of these modes reflects the dual nature of the *Low-Re* stall process—separation-driven instabilities coupled with radial migration and blockage. Once CT is introduced, both *Re* conditions exhibit over 95% KE concentrated in the first mode pair. The associated fluctuation regions are localized near the slots, indicating that the extraction-reinjection action directly governs the dominant unsteady dynamics.

FIGURE 15: POD MODES AND SNAPSHOT OF FLOWFIELD FLUCTUATIONS FOR AXIAL VELOCITY AT 98% SPAN FOR REF. RE

FIGURE 16: POD MODES AND SNAPSHOT OF FLOWFIELD FLUCTUATIONS FOR AXIAL VELOCITY AT 98% SPAN FOR LOW RE

While the spatial patterns are similar across *Re* conditions, the temporal response reveals a critical distinction. Figures 17 and 18 show the phase-locked averages of the first two modal coefficients at *Ref. Re* and *Low Re*, with the slot momentum flux ΔM_f used as the trigger signal. At *Ref. Re*, coefficient a_1 peaks at the instant of maximum net flux (0°), while a_2 nearly vanishes. When a_2 peaks, a_1 is minimal, demonstrating an orthogonal phase relationship. This symmetry indicates that extraction and reinjection are balanced, and the slot functions as a transient momentum exchanger. The small standard deviation further confirms the strong repeatability of this phase-symmetric process. At *Low Re*, however, a_1 nearly vanishes at 0° , and the dominant response is projected onto a_2 , indicating a phase offset relative to the net-flux peak. This offset directly reflects the dominance of extraction. If extraction and reinjection were

balanced, the net-flux peak would synchronize with the principal mode, as observed at *Ref. Re*. This behavior aligns with the macroscopic impulse analysis, where extraction exceeds reinjection by approximately 11.3% at *Low Re*. The larger standard deviation also reflects stronger cycle-to-cycle variability, indicating that stability enhancement under *low-Re* conditions relies on persistent suction rather than symmetric extraction–reinjection exchange.

In summary, POD analysis demonstrates that CT stabilization adapts to *Re*: at *Ref. Re*, the slot acts as a phase-symmetric momentum exchanger, whereas at *Low Re*, it serves as a persistent extraction-driven stabilizer. This phase-based interpretation provides direct evidence for a fundamental shift in stabilization mechanisms between *Re* values.

FIGURE 17: PHASE-LOCKED AVERAGES OF THE FIRST TWO MODAL COEFFICIENTS AT REF. RE, SYNCHRONIZED TO THE NET SLOT MOMENTUM FLUX

FIGURE 18: PHASE-LOCKED AVERAGES OF THE FIRST TWO MODAL COEFFICIENTS AT LOW RE, SYNCHRONIZED TO THE NET SLOT MOMENTUM FLUX

4. CONCLUSION

At *Ref. Re*, stall onset is governed by interaction between TLV and passage shock, inducing vortex breakdown and blockage. The associated power spectrum features a strong response near $1.237f_{BPF}$ and its harmonic, consistent with vortex-shock coupling. At *Low Re*, the dominant mechanism shifts to radial migration and suction-side separation: TLV remains relatively stable, and weaker shocks result in diminished vortex-shock interaction. High amplitudes at $0.392f_{BPF}$ and $0.784f_{BPF}$ in the power spectrum correspond to the periodic evolution of SV and RSV, reflecting a fundamentally distinct vorticity-generation process.

At *Ref. Re*, extraction and reinjection impulses within one passage are nearly balanced, confirming that the slot acts as a transient momentum exchanger—removing low-energy fluid while energizing the mainstream. At *Low Re*, reinjection weakens and extraction dominates, with net extraction impulse exceeding reinjection by approximately 11.3%. This sustained extraction mitigates radial migration and stabilizes the suction-side boundary layer, consistent with the reduced frequency content of the flow. Combined analysis of slot mass flux, momentum flux, and integrated impulse reveals a fundamental shift from balanced exchange to suction-biased stabilization.

POD of the 98% span plane identifies the dominant flow structures driving stall in the baseline rotor, validating the physical interpretation of stall mechanisms. With the CT applied, the spatial distribution of dominant modes remains similar at both *Re*, indicating engagement of the same structures. Their temporal characteristics, however, differ: phase-triggered averaging of modal coefficients against net slot momentum flux shows that at *Ref. Re*, the a_1 mode synchronizes with the net flux peak, whereas at *Low Re*, the modal vector is phase-shifted such that a_1 is smaller at maximum flux. This temporal offset directly reflects the transition from symmetric exchange to sustained extraction as the slot’s controlling mechanism.

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